

REVIEW ON PHYTOCHEMICAL AND PHARMACOLOGICAL PROFILE OF *RICINUS COMMUNIS* AND *CALOTROPIS PROCERA*

¹Chhavi, ²Chanchal Malhotra

¹M.Sc. Student, ²Assistant Professor,

^{1,2}Department of Botany

Baba Mastnath University, Asthal Bohar, Rohtak, Haryana

E-mail: chanchalmalhotra2007@rediffmail.com

KEYWORDS

Phytoconstituents,
Calotropis procera,
Ricinus communis

ABSTRACT

Medicinal plants have been used as a primary source of medicine since ancient times. Many of the currently available medicines can be obtained directly in extract form or as a modified synthetic form. Plants have the ability to produce goods that are helpful to us, such as phytoconstituents, which are employed to perform biological processes and defend us against predators like viruses, fungus, and other bacteria. One of the most successful ways for discovering novel medications is to use phytoconstituents derived from natural materials. The plants contain various classes of bioactive secondary metabolites such as terpenoids, flavonoids, saponins, steroids and cardiac glycosides. Phytochemicals reported from the *Calotropis* plant were sterols, flavonoids, alkaloids, saponins, tannins, and hydrocarbons were isolated from the plant. Due to presence of these phytochemicals the plant is known to possess a wide range of pharmacological activities such as anticancer, acaricidal, schizonticidal, antimicrobial, anthelmintic, insecticidal, anti-inflammatory, antidiarrheal, anticancerous, and larvicidal activities with other beneficial properties. In this review, focus has been given on the phytochemical and pharmacological properties of *Calotropis procera* and *Ricinus communis*.

1. INTRODUCTION

Since prehistoric times, herbal plants have always been a valuable source of medicine. Synthetic medications are still difficult to get by in several developing and impoverished countries' isolated rural areas. Many people employ traditional medicinal herbs to cure a range of diseases because they are

readily available. 65-70 percent of India's rural population depends on medicinal plants in the form of indigenous ethnic systems such as Ayurveda, Siddha, Unani and others. The use of herbal medicine has grown quite popular not only in India, but all around the world. The estimated global herbal market was 63.05 billion US\$ in 2014, which became 71.9 billion US\$ in 2016(Choudhury *et al.*, 2020). Herbal components are considered more efficient and safer than chemical equivalents but still, the absolute absence of any adverse effect might not be possible. (Kim *et al.*, 2021).

A medicinal plant is one that has chemicals can which can be used for therapeutic purposes or that contains chemo-pharmaceutical synthesis precursors. Plants have long been used to cure a variety of disorders, including infectious diseases like diarrhoea, fever, and colds, as well as birth control and dental hygiene. Furthermore, many psychotropic drugs used in traditional medicine are derived from plants. Traditional medicinal herbs have a wide range of effects. The use of plants and their extracts in the formulation of herbal medicines laid the groundwork for current therapeutic sciences, enabling man to develop an empirical medicine. As a result, various plant species are being screened for herbal chemicals, and the compounds are also being extracted from the plants. Secondary metabolites, a varied set of compounds that include alkaloids, glycosides, amines, insecticides, steroids, flavonoids, and related metabolites, are abundant in medicinal plants and have been widely exploited in the medicine and pharmaceutical industries (Edoga *et al.*, 2005). Many plants secondary metabolites are constitutive and present in physiologically active forms in healthy plants, whereas others exist as inactive precursors that are released in response to tissue damage or pathogen attack. Plant materials beneficial medicinal effects are usually due to a combination of secondary metabolites found in the plants. Countless no. of plants have been reported for their medicinal effects. Medicinal plants usually include a combination of chemical compounds that work individually, additively, or synergistically to promote health. Bitter substances that aid digestion, anti-inflammatory compounds that reduce swelling and pain, phenolic compounds that act as antioxidants and venotonics, antibacterial and antifungal tannins that act as natural antibiotics, diuretic substances that aid in the elimination of waste products and toxins, and alkaloids that improve mood and provide a sense of well-being can all be found in a single plant (Gurib -Fabki, 2006).

2. History of Medicinal Plant Research

The initial isolation of active principles alkaloids such as morphine, strychnine, quinine, and other alkaloids in the early 19th century initiated a new era in the use of medicinal plants and the commencement of modern medicinal plant research. With the enormous growth of synthetic pharmaceutical chemistry and microbial fermentation after 1945, the emphasis switched away from plant-derived medications. During this time, plant metabolites were mostly studied from a phytochemical and chemotaxonomic standpoint. However, interest in medications derived from plants and maybe animals has progressively increased over the last decade (Hamburger M and Hostettmann

K, 1991). Physicians began extracting chemical compounds from therapeutic plants as chemical science and pharmacognosy advanced. Some examples of therapeutic plant products include quinine, which was identified from *Cinchona* by French pharmacists Peletier and Caventou in 1920. Hoffmann, a German chemist, discovered Aspirin in the willow bark in the mid-nineteenth century. Plant-based medicines began to be replaced more and more with purified chemicals, which were more powerful and easier to prescribe and give, as the active components in medicinal plants were identified and extracted (Harvey A, 2000).

Due to the usage of the "more powerful and potent synthetic drug" in the first half of the twenty-first century, phytomedicines were on the verge of extinction. Due to the various side effects of modern treatments, the usefulness of medicinal plants is being rediscovered, as some of them have been shown to be as effective as synthetic medicines with fewer or no side effects or limitations. It has been proven that, while the effects of natural remedies may appear to be slower at first, the long-term results are sometimes better, especially in chronic disorders (Akunyili).

The 19th century marked the isolation of numerous alkaloids from plants species used as drugs, namely, atropine (*Atropa belladonna*), caffeine (*Coffea arabica*), cocaine (*Erythroxylum coca*), ephedrine (*Ephedra species*), morphine and codeine (*Papaver somniferum*), pilocarpine (*Pilocarpus jaborandi* Holmes), physostigmine (*Physostigma venenosum*), quinine (*Cinchona cordifolia*), salicin (*Salix species*), theobromine (*Theobroma cacao*), theophylline (*Camellia sinensis*) and (+)-tubocurarine (*Chondodendron tomentosum*). Following these discoveries, bioactive secondary metabolites from plants were later utilized more widely as medicines, both in their original and modified forms (Raskin *et al.*, 2002).

3. Phytochemicals

Phytochemicals can have complementary and/or overlapping mechanisms of action in the body, including antioxidant effects, modulation of enzyme actions, stimulation of the immune system, modulation of hormone metabolism, anti-bacterial and antiviral effect, interference with DNA replication and physical action whereby some may bind physically to cell walls thereby preventing the adhesion of pathogens to human cell walls (Ngoci *et al.*, 2011). Some of these phytochemicals are discussed in the following sections.

3.1 Alkaloids

An alkaloid is a poisonous or physiologically active plant-derived chemical. Some alkaloids, such as isopteropodine and pteropopine, have antimicrobial properties, encouraging the removal of dangerous microbes and cell debris by white blood cells (Ogunwenmo *et al.*, 2007). Berberine, piperine, and harmane are highly aromatic planarquaternary alkaloids that function by intercalating the DNA and cell wall (Cowan, 1999). Others influence the central nervous system (CNS) at synapses by imitating neurotransmitters such as acetylcholine, dopamine, and serotonin. They also act as narcotics, antimalarials,

and ophthalmic topical anaesthetics in the treatment of hypertension, neuralgia, rheumatism, motion sickness, and hormone longevity. They are used to relieve pain in cases of boils, infected wounds, and complaints such as headaches, abdominal pains, and eye diseases because they contain analgesic effect. They also have anticancer properties; for example, indole alkaloids are used in treatment for leukaemia and Hodgkin's disease. They work by depolymerizing and terminating the protein microtubules that make up the mitotic spindle during cell division. This procedure aids in the prevention of tumour cells from splitting or dividing, resulting in cancer decrease. However, some alkaloids are hallucinogenic, addictive, and deadly, and are thus utilised as arrow poison in wild animal hunting (Ogunwenmo *et al.*, 2007; Ngoci *et al.*, 2011).

3.2 Tannins

Tannins are astringent, bitter plant polyphenols that attach to proteins and cause them to precipitate or shrink. They modulate oxidative stress and prevent degenerative illnesses by functioning as antioxidants through free radical scavenging activity, chelation of transition metals, inhibition of prooxidative enzymes, and lipid peroxidation (Navarro *et al.*, 2003); (Vit *et al.*, 2008; Ngoci *et al.*, 2011). They also slow tumour growth by triggering apoptosis (Scalbert *et al.*, 2005) and reducing carcinogen mutagenicity (Okuda, 2005; Ngoci *et al.*, 2011). They have antimicrobial activity by hydrogen bonding, covalent bonding, and nonspecific interactions to complex nucleophilic proteins. Cell wall and cell membrane adhesion proteins are the main targets for complexing, resulting in the inactivation of microbial adhesion, which is the initial stage in the development of infections. By interacting with estrogen receptors, they play an endocrine role. They're also anti-inflammatory and molluscicidal, making them useful in the fight against schistosomiasis. They're also antidiarrheal, antiseptic, antifungal, antiparasitic, and anti-irritant, and they're used to stop bleeding, heal wounds, and improve vascular health by decreasing peptides that harden arteries (Awoyinka *et al.*, 2007); (Ogunwenmo *et al.*, 2007); (Ngoci *et al.*, 2011). They also have an economic role in the leather sector by tanning leathers. Nonetheless, they have an impact on cattle feed intake and digestion, and excessive amounts might be carcinogenic to normal tissues (Scalbert *et al.*, 2005); (Ngoci *et al.*, 2011).

3.3 Flavonoids

They are phenolic and water soluble structural derivatives of flavones that contain conjugated aromatic systems and are commonly attached to sugar(s) as glycosides (Harborne, 1973). They function as antioxidants, thereby guarding against degenerative diseases. Flavonoids like quercetin act as chain-breaking antioxidants, preventing macrophages and metal ions like copper from oxidising low-density lipoprotein. Oxidative stress is reduced as a result of this (Ngoci *et al.*, 2011). They also act as anti-allergens, anti-inflammatory agents, and trigger phase two enzymes that remove mutagens and carcinogens (Ogunwenmo *et al.*, 2007); (Ngoci *et al.*, 2011). They also operate as antimicrobials by complexing extracellular and soluble proteins, as well as the cell wall of bacteria. Microbial membranes

may be disrupted by more lipophilic flavonoids (Navarro *et al.*, 2003); (Al-Bayati and Al-Mola, 2008); (Samy and Gopalakrishnakone, 2008); (Kaur and Arora, 2009); (Ngoci *et al.*, 2011). Flavonoids have also been shown to improve coronary flow, lower myocardial oxygen consumption, and lower blood pressure (Dong *et al.*, 2005); (Ngoci *et al.*, 2011). They're also known to minimise capillary fragility (Harborne, 1973), are anti-allergic, and anti-spasmodic, therefore they're used to treat asthma and nosebleeds (Ngoci *et al.*, 2011). Flavonoids with no hydroxyl groups (-OH) on their structure are more active against microbes than those with -OH, implying that the membrane is their microbiological target. (Cowan, 1999); (Samy and Gopalakrishnakone, 2008); (Ngoci *et al.*, 2011).

3.4 Saponins

These are soap-like surface active agents that can be identified by their capacity to generate foaming and haemolyse blood cells (Harborne, 1973). They perform a variety of biological functions, including stimulating the respiratory system as an expectorant and thus cough activity. They also have anti-protozoa properties, such as triggering cell lysis by interacting with cholesterol in protozoal cell membranes. Yucca saponins are efficient against *Giardia lamblia*, a protozoan. By serving as an adjuvant, they act as vaccine boosters. Anti-inflammatory, emetic, antiviral, antifungal, insecticidal, molluscicidal, piscidal, and antibacterial properties are all present in them (Ngoci *et al.*, 2011). The antibacterial effects are mediated via saponin's membranolytic capabilities as well as a reduction in the extracellular medium's surface tension (Al-Bayati and Al-Mola, 2008). They have anti-cancer properties without harming healthy cells. This is accomplished by interacting with the cholesterol-rich membranes of cancer cells and causing mitotic arrest, which results in cell apoptosis (Ngoci *et al.*, 2011). Cell division and expansion are slowed as a result of this. They also bind to primary bile acids, which are converted into secondary bile acids by intestinal bacteria. Colon cancer promoters include several secondary bile acids. They are economically valuable as a source of low-cost, eco-friendly detergents and cosmetics (Ngoci *et al.*, 2011). Also, several saponins, such as Radix Notoginseng, have been shown to improve coronary artery blood flow, prevent platelet aggregation, and reduce heart muscle oxygen consumption (Dong *et al.*, 2005). Anti-edema, antitussive, purgative, and immunoregulatory activities are also present. (Ngoci *et al.*, 2011).

3.5 Glycosides

Glycosides are the condensation products of sugars with a wide range of organic hydroxyl or thiol compounds, with the hemiacetal moiety of the carbohydrate playing an insignificant role in the condensation process. Strophanthidin from *Strophanthus*, digitoxin from *Digitalis*, barbaloin from *Aloes*, salicin from *Salix*, cantharidin from *Cantharides*, and prunasin from *Prunus* are examples of glycosides. This class of medications is typically used to increase appetite and improve digestion. Glycosides are simply bitter components that are widely found in Gentianaceae family that, despite being chemically unrelated, share the trait of having a highly bitter taste. The bitters stimulate the flow

of saliva and gastric juices by acting on the gustatory nerves. Bitter principles have a lactone group in their structure, which might be diterpene lactones (as in andrographolide) or triterpenoids (as in amarogentin). Due to the presence of tannic acid, several bitter components are utilised as astringents, antiprotozoal agents, or to lower thyroxine and metabolism. Amarogentin, gentiopicrinandrographolide, ailanthone, and polygala are examples of cardiac glycosides (acts on the heart), anthracene glycosides (purgative and for the treatment of skin problems), chalcone glycoside (anticancer), and chalcone glycoside (anticancer) (Ogunwenmo *et al.*, 2007); (Ngoci *et al.*, 2011).

3.6 Phenols

Phenolics, phenols, or polyphenolics (or polyphenol extracts) are chemical components that are found in abundance as natural colour pigments in plants' fruits. Phenolics are largely produced in plants from phenylalanine by phenylalanine ammonia lyase (PAL). They are vital to plants and serve a variety of purposes. Plant defence against pathogens and herbivore predators may play the most essential function, and hence they are used in the control of human pathogenic illnesses (Ogunwenmo *et al.*, 2007); (Ngoci *et al.*, 2011).

4. Biological Activities of Phytochemicals

Table 1. Biological function of various Phytochemicals in Medicinal Plants (Saxena *et al.*, 2013)

Classification	Main groups of compounds	Biological function
NSA (Non-starch poly-saccharides.)	Cellulose, hemicellulose, gums, mucilages, pectins, lignins	Water holding capacity, delay in nutrient absorption, binding toxins and bile acids
Antibacterial & Antifungal	Terpenoids, alkaloids, phenolics	Inhibitors of micro-organisms, reduce the risk of fungal infection
Antioxidants	Polyphenolic compounds, flavonoids, carotenoids, tocopherols, ascorbic acid	Oxygen free radical quenching, inhibition of lipid peroxidation
Anticancer	Carotenoids, polyphenols, curcumine, Flavonoids	Inhibitors of tumor, inhibited develop
Detoxifying Agents	Reductive acids, tocopherols, phenols, indoles, aromatic isothiocyanates, coumarins,	Inhibitors of procarcinogen activation, inducers of drug

	flavones, carotenoids, retinoids, cyanates, phytosterols	binding of carcinogens, inhibitors of tumourogenesis
Other	Alkaloids, terpenoids, volatile flavor compounds, biogenic amines	Neuropharmacological agents, anti-oxidants, cancer chemoprevention

5. Plant Description *Ricinus communis* and *Calotropis procera*

5.1 *Ricinus communis*

- Kingdom: Plantae
- Phylum: Spermatophyta
- Subphylum: Angiospermae
- Class: Dicotyledonae
- Order: Euphorbiales
- Family: Euphorbiaceae
- Genus: *Ricinus*
- Species: *communis*

It is a resistant shrub or small tree with a softly woody stem that can reach a height of 4 metres. Smooth, spherical, and frequently red stems with clear sap. The leaves are simple and arranged in an alternate manner. Near the middle of the leaf blades, long purple leaf stalks are connected. These are large, star-shaped fruits with sharply toothed margins; their colour is shiny dark green or reddish on top and paler on the bottom; when crushed, they emit an odour. The flowers are arranged in terminal spikes, with creamy male flowers (3-5) at the bottom and reddish female flowers (1-7) at the top. The fruit is a three-lobed, spiky, greenish to reddish purple capsule with large, oval, glossy, bean-like seeds that are highly poisonous and have a varied brownish colour.

Castor oil, extracted from the plant's seed, is still widely used in traditional and herbal medicine. After the oil was removed and boiled to destroy the poison, the plant's seed was used as fertiliser and mixed into animal feed. Castor oil is primarily used as a purgative and as a laxative. It's also used to make soaps, printer's ink, plastics, fibres, hydraulic fluid, braking fluid, varnishes, paints, embalming fluid, textile dyes, leather finishes, adhesives, waxes, and fungicides, among other things. Phytochemicals such as alkaloids, flavonoids, terpenes, saponins, and phenolic compounds such as kaempferol, gallic acid, ricin, rutin, lupeol, ricinoleic acid, pinene, thujone, and gentsic acid have been discovered in various investigations. Anticancer, antibacterial, insecticidal, antioxidant, anti-diabetic, antinociceptive, anti-inflammatory, bone regenerating, analgesic, and anticonvulsant activity are among the pharmacological and therapeutic actions of these phytochemicals. (Jena, J. *et al.*, 2012).

5.1.1 Phytochemical constituents of *Ricinus communis*

The plant *Ricinus* has some very important phytochemical constituents e.g. flavonoids, saponins, alkaloids and steroids (Jena and Kumar Gupta, 2012). Due to the presence of these metabolites *R. communis* is reported to possess antioxidant (Nemudzivhadi and Masoko, 2014), anti-implantation (Makonnen *et al.* 1999), anti-inflammatory (Srivastava *et al.*, 2014), antidiabetic (Shokeen *et al.*, 2008), central analgesic (Mim and Chowdhury, 2015), antitumour (Lin and Liu, 1986), larvicidal (Rampadarath and Puchooa, 2016) and antiasthmatic (Taur and Patil, 2011) properties.

(Kang, S.S *et al.*, 1985) did the Preliminary Phytochemical study of *R. communis* which showed the presence of steroids, saponins, alkaloids, flavonoids, and glycosides. The dried leaves of *R. communis* showed the presence of two alkaloids, ricinine(0.55%) and N-demethylricinine(0.016%) and six flavones glycosides kaempferol-3-O- β -D-glucopyranoside kaempferol-3-O- β -D-xylopyranoside, quercetin-3-O- β -D-xylopyranoside, quercetin-3-O- β -D-glucopyranoside, kaempferol-3-O- β -rutoside and quercetin-3-O- β -rutoside .the monoterpenoids (1, 8-cineole, camphor and α pinene)and a sesquiterpenoid (β -caryophyllene), gallic acid, quercetin, gentisic acid, rutin, epicatechin and ellagic acid are the major phenolic compounds isolated from leaves.

Peter Hermann Stillmark (1888) described *Ricinus* as one of the most poisonous plant due to the existence of a naturally occurring protein, ricin, when he tested the extract of beans on red blood cells and observed them to agglutinate.

5.1.2 Pharmacological activity of *R. communis*

5.1.2.1 Anti- fertility activity

Preliminary Phytochemical Assays for Steroids and Alkaloids demonstrate that methanol extracts of *R. communis* seed are positive (Sandhya kumary *et al.*, 2003). The pituitary gland releases gonadotrophins in response to sex hormones via both positive and negative feedback mechanisms in the luteal phase of the menstrual cycle due to the combined influence of oestrogen and progesterone. In addition, the pituitary gland inhibits the production of luteinizing hormone (LH) and follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH). Finally, it helps to suppress ovarian follicle maturation, which prevents ovulation. Because the sex hormone is a steroidal component, the presence of steroids in the methanol extract of *Ricinus communis* seed causes anti-fertility effects (phytosterols).

5.1.2.2 Anti -inflammatory activity

(Saini *et al.*, 2010) looked into the anti-inflammatory properties of *R. communis* and found that doses of *R. communis* methanolic leaves extract of 250 and 500 mg/kg have a protective effect in preventing cellular events during edoema development and all stages of acute inflammation. The anti-inflammatory

effect of *R. communis* methanolic extract was attributed to the presence of flavonoids, which protect rats from carrageenan-induced paw oedema.

5.1.2.3 Anti-microbial activity

(Mathur *et al.*, 2011) demonstrated that several solvent extracts of *Ricinus communis* roots (200mg/ml) have antimicrobial activity against pathogenic microorganisms such as *E. coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aer*. The antibacterial activity of the hexane and methanol extracts was the highest, while the aqueous extracts had no appreciable antimicrobial activity.

5.1.2.4 Anti –asthmatic effect

(Dnyaneshwar *et al.*, 2011) Because of its antiallergic and mast cell stabilising properties, the ethanolic root extract of *R. communis* is beneficial in the treatment of asthma. Saponins reduce basophil histamine and neutrophil beta glucuronidase release, and flavonoids have smooth muscle relaxant and bronchodilator activity. Apigenin and luteolin-like flavonoids inhibit basophil histamine and neutrophil beta glucuronidase release and have antiallergic effect in vivo. The ethanolic extract of *R. communis* decreases milk-induced leucocytosis and eosinophilia and has an antiasthmatic action due to the presence of flavonoids or saponins. Using clonidine-induced catalepsy in mice, the ethanol extract of *R. communis* root showed antihistaminic action at doses of 100, 125, and 150 mg/kg intraperitoneally (Dnyaneshwar *et al.*, 2011).

5.1.2.5 Anti -diabetic effect

Bioassays were used to study the purification of an ethanolic extract of *Ricinus communis* roots (Shokeen. *et al.*, 2008). Fasting blood glucose, total lipid profile, liver, and kidney functions were all improved after diabetic rats were given the effective dose (500mg/kg b. w) of RCRE for 20 days. The antihyperglycemic activity of the R-18 fraction is the highest of all the fractions. There was no significant difference in alkaline phosphatase, serum bilirubin, creatinine, seru pyruvate transaminases, or total protein after administration of the extract at a dose of 10 g/kg b.wt. As a result, *R. communis* is a useful diabetes herbal remedy.

5.1.2.6 Anti-oxidant activity

Castor oil's active ingredients offer wound-healing capabilities, since they provide antioxidant activity and inhibit lipid peroxidation. According to a comparison study of two different concentrations (5 percent w/w and 10 percent w/w) of castor oil, the 10 percent w/w Castor oil ointment exhibited better wound-healing qualities (Prasad M. K. *et al.*, 2011).

5.1.2.7 Insecticidal activity

The leaf extract of *R. communis* shows molluscicidal efficiency against *Lymnaea acuminata* due to active components such as castor oil and ricinine, however the seed extracts have greater insecticidal and insectistatic action than the leaf extracts against *frugiperda*. Mosquitoes such as *Anopheles arabiensis*, *Callosobruchus chinensis*, and *Culex quinquefasciatus* are all susceptible to *R. communis* aqueous leaf extracts (Ramos-Lopez *et al.*, 2010; Elimam *et al.*, 2009).

5.2. Plant *Calotropis procera*

- Kingdom: Plantae
- Phylum: Spermatophyta
- Subphylum: Angiospermae
- Class: Dicotyledonae
 - Order: Gentianales
 - Genus: *Calotropis*
 - Species: *procera*

It's a big shrub with waxy stems and milky sap on its leaves. It has broad greyish-green leaves that are borne in pairs and are stem-clasping (5–20 cm long and 4–10 cm broad). It has five white petals with reddish-colored tips and a purplish crown-like centre on its flowers (20–30 mm across). The bladderly "pod" is a big (8–12 cm long) greyish-green bladderly fruit. When the fruit ripens, it cracks apart, releasing a tuft of long, white, silky hairs on top of each seed.

Calotropis is used to treat digestive problems including dysentery, constipation, and stomach ulcers, as well as painful illnesses like dental problems, cramps, and joint pain, as well as parasitic infections like elephantiasis and worms. *Calotropis* is used to treat syphilis, boils, inflammation (swelling), epilepsy, hysteria, fever, muscle spasms, warts, leprosy, gout, snakebites, and cancer, among other things. (Nadkarni A.K and Nadkarni K.M, 1960) Smoke from the bark is inhaled for coughs, asthma, and to promote sweating in inhalation therapy. (Parihar, G. *et al.*, 2016).

5.2.1 Phytochemical constituents of *Calotropis procera*

(Parihar and Balekar) showed that the leaf of the *C.procera* consists of cardenolides 162 mg/g at dry weight and 2 mg/g total dry weight. The important cardenolides found in the plant are voruscharin, uscharidin, uzarigenin, calotroposide, calactin, calotoxin, uscharin, ascleposide, calotropagenin, coroglaucigenin, calotropin, proceroside, proceragenin, and syriogenin. (Saber *et al.*, 1969). Shukla OP, Krishnamurthy CR has reported that besides the cardenolides, other phytochemicals are also identified from the plant such as sterols, flavonoids, coumarins, alkaloids, triterpenes, saponins, tannins, and hydrocarbons were isolated from the plant. The major flavonoid is rutin (quercetin-3-rutinoside). The

leaves contain ascorbic acid, calactin, calotoxin, calatropagenin, calotropin, polysaccharide containing D-arabinose, D-glucose, D-glucosamine and L-rhamnose, calotropagenin, and 3-proteinase. The latex contains calotropin, α -calotropeol, 3-epimoretenol, gigantol, giganteol, isogiganteol, α -lactuceryl acetate, α -lactucerylisovalerate, lupeol, proceroside, proceragenin, syriogenin, taraxast-20 α - (30)-en-(4-methyl-3-pentenoate), 3'-thiazoline cardenolideuscharidin, uzarigenin, voruscharin and β -sitosterol, powerful bacteriolytic enzyme in latex.

5.2.2. Pharmacological activity

C. procera is also utilised as a treatment for skin diseases, elephantiasis, toothaches, asthma, leprosy, and rheumatism by numerous cultures around the world (Sharma *et al.*, 2011). Different parts of the *C. procera* plant, including as the leaves, roots and bark, flower, fruits, stem, and latex, have been identified to contain numerous phytochemicals that may have distinct pharmacological actions. With other beneficial effects, the coarse shrub is acaricidal, schizonticidal, antimicrobial, anthelmintic, insecticidal, anti-inflammatory, antidiarrheal, anticancerous, and larvicidal. Calotropin, calotropagenin, calotoxin, calactin, uscharin, amyryl, amyryl esters, uscharidin, coroglaucigenin, frugoside, corotoxigenin, calotropagenin, and voruscharine are cardiotoxic substances found in the plant that are utilised in the medicinal treatment (Ahmed *et al.*, 2005).

5.2.2.1 Anti-diabetic effect

Sayed *et al.*, 2016 investigated the antioxidant activity and antidiabetic effect of dried latex of *C. procera* in alloxan-induced diabetes rats. The oral doses of DL were 100 and 400 mg/kg, respectively. The findings showed a drop in blood glucose and an increase in hepatic glycogen content. (Tsala *et al.*,) investigated the antioxidant efficacy of a *C. procera* bark ethanol extract against surgical wounds.

5.2.2.2. Anti-malarial activity

According to Meena. *et al.*, 2010, the most potent ethanolic extracts of *C. procera* were flower and bud extracts, with IC50 values ranging from 0.11 to 0.47 mg/ml against *Plasmodium falciparum* MRC20 CQ-sensitive strain and 0.52 to 1.22 mg/ml against MRC 76 CQ-resistant strain. Despite being 220, 440 times less effective than CQ, these extracts need additional investigation in order to identify the active ingredients.

5.2.2.3. Anti-cancer activity

The antitumor bioactive chemical proceraside was discovered via molecular docking with macromolecules involved in the cell cycle and DNA replication (Gurung *et al.*, 2016).

5.2.2.4. Anti- microbial activity

Using agar well diffusion and paper disc methods (Khairnar *et al.*, 2012) investigated the antimicrobial effect of ethanol, aqueous, and chloroform extracts of *C. procera* leaf and latex on five bacteria (*Escherichia coli*, *S. aureus*, *Staphylococcus albus*, *Streptococcus pyogenes*, and *Streptococcus pneumoniae*). The results showed that ethanol was the best extracting solvent for antibacterial characteristics of *C. procera* leaf and latex, followed by chloroform and water in that order.

5.2.2.5. Anti-diarrheal activity

The dried leaves of *C. procera* were tested for antidiarrheal activity by (Quazi, S. *et al.*, 2013). In 80 percent of rats treated with castor oil, a single oral dose of DL (500 mg/kg) resulted in a significant decrease in the frequency of defecation and the severity of diarrhoea, as well as protection from diarrhoea.

5.2.2.6. Toxicity

According to Parihar *et al.*, 2016, the plant has been demonstrated to be poisonous, and it is one of the few plants that grazing animals avoid. Tribal people have utilised the latex from the plant to construct poison arrows for hunting purposes. Latex is highly harmful to human eyes, causing ocular toxicity and photophobia, as well as eyesight loss. The inflammatory effects of *C. procera* latex were investigated in rats using pedal edoema and air pouch models of inflammation, and the latex might be utilised to test anti-inflammatory medicines. When latex is mistakenly administered to the eye, it causes toxic iridocyclitis, keratoconjunctivitis, corneal endothelial cytotoxicity, and keratitis.

6. Influence of environmental factors on phytochemicals

Environmental and soil conditions have a big influence on phytochemical accumulation in plants, which can affect their nutritional and therapeutic characteristics. The quantitative and qualitative composition of metabolites is affected by local geographic-climatic circumstances, seasonal variations, and external conditions such as light intensity, temperature range, water availability, and soil composition. For example, when altitude increased, the berberine concentration of *Berberis asiatica* decreased (Andola *et al.*, 2010). In *Hedychium spicatum*, on the other hand, phenolic content increased as altitude climbed. (Rawat *et al.*, 2011), etc. These studies demonstrate that environmental conditions have an impact on a species' responses to secondary metabolites. Previous research on *V. jatamansi*'s morphological and genetic diversity suggests that environmental and genetic factors influence the plant's diversity and chemical composition (Jugran *et al.*, 2013). However, there has been little systematic research on the species' sensitivity to secondary metabolites and antioxidant activity across its altitudinal range and ecological circumstances. This is significant since the species grow in a variety of habitats across a broad altitudinal range, with microclimatic variables such as temperature, moisture regime, and soil nutrients varying greatly (Rawal *et al.*, 2003).

Sunayana *et al.*, 2017 investigated the difference in nutritional and phytochemical properties of *W. tinctoria* in different forest sites in North Gujarat, with the goal of determining the impact of onsite soil variables on the species' phytochemical and nutrient levels. Localities and plant parts showed substantial differences in phytochemical, nutritional content, and antioxidant activity. Total phenolic, flavonoid, flavonol, saponin, and protein content were higher in leaves, while total alkaloid content was highest in fruits. Total phenolic ($p < 0.01$) and flavonol ($p < 0.05$) in leaves had a negative association with soil phosphorus, but protein in stem bark had a positive relationship ($p < 0.01$). Saponin levels in leaves were found to be substantially associated ($p < 0.05$) with total nitrogen and carbon levels in the soil. The findings suggest that soil elements may have a role in the buildup of total phenolic content, total flavonoid content, and antioxidant activity in *W. tinctoria* above ground systems.

7. CONCLUSION

The results indicated that the plants investigated contained medicinally important constituents. Many previous investigations had accumulated evidence that the reported phytochemicals were bioactive. Several studies have demonstrated that these phytochemicals contribute pharmacological and physiological characteristics to the plants researched in the treatment of various illnesses. As a result, extracts from these plants could be considered a promising source of therapeutics. Further effort should be done to separate, purify, and characterise the active ingredients responsible for the activity of these plants, as well as further work to isolate, purify, and describe the active compounds responsible for the activity of these plants. In addition, more research into the potential mechanisms of action of these extracts is encouraged.

8. REFERENCES

1. Ahmed, K.K., Rana, A.C., Dixit, V.K. (2005). *Calotropis* species (Asclepiaceae): A comprehensive review. *Pharmacogn Mag*, 1, 48-52.
2. Akunyili, D.N.(2013). The role of regulation of medicinal plants and phytomedicine in socio-economic development. *AGM/SC of the Nigerian Society of Pharmacognosy*.
3. Ali, S.S., Kasoju, N., Luthra, A., Singh, A., Sharanabasava, H., Sahuand, A., Bora, U. (2008). Indian medicinal herbs as source of antioxidants. *Food Res. Int*, 41, 1-15.
4. Alonso-Amelot, M. E., Oliveros-Bastidas, A., and Calcagno-Pisarelli, M. (2007). Phenolics and condensed tannins of high altitude *Pteridium arachnoideum* in relation to sunlight exposure, elevation, and rain regime. *Biochemical Systematics and Ecology*, 35, 1–7.
5. Andola, H. C., Gaira, K. S., Rawal, R. S., Rawat, M. S. M., and Bhatt, I. D. (2010). Habitat dependent variation in berberine content of *Berberis asiatica* Roxb. Ex. DC. In *Kumaon, western Himalaya. Chemistry and Biodiversity*, 7, 415–420.
6. Antherden, L.M. (1969). *Textbook of Pharmaceutical Chemistry*, Oxford University Press, London, , 8, 813-814.

7. Brown, J.E., Rice-Evans, C.A. (1998). Luteolin rich artichoke extract protects low density lipoprotein from oxidation in vitro. *Free Radical Res*, 29, 247-255.
8. Choudhury, P.R., Talukdar, A.D., Nath, D., Saha, P and Nath, R. (2020). Traditional folk medicine and drug discovery: prospects and outcome in advances in pharmaceutical biotechnology. *Publisher Springer Singapore*, 3-13.
9. Dai, J., Mumper, R. (2010). Plant phenolics: extraction, analysis and their antioxidant and anticancer properties. *Molecules*, 15, 7313-7352.
10. Del-Rio, A., Obdulio, B.G., Casfillo, J., Main, F.G., Ortuno, A. (1997). Uses and properties of citrus flavonoids. *J. Agric. Food Chem*, 45, 4505-4515.
11. Edoga, H.O., Okwu, D.E., Mbaebie, B.O. (2005). Phytochemicals constituents of some Nigerian medicinal plants. *Afr. J. Biotechnol*, 4(7), 685-688.
12. Elimam, A.M., Elmalik, K.H. and Ali, F.S. (2009). Larvicidal, adult emergence inhibition and oviposition deterrent effects of foliage extract from *Ricinus communis L.* against *Anopheles arabiensis* and *Culex Quinquefasciatus* in Sudan. *In Tropical Biomedicine*, 26(2), 130–139.
13. Ghasemzadeh, A., Jaafar, H. Z. E., Rahmat, A., Wahab, P. E. M., and Halim, M. R. A. (2010). Effect of different light intensities on total phenolics and flavonoids synthesis and anti-oxidant activities in young ginger varieties (*Zingiber officinale Roscoe*). *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 11, 3885–3897.
14. Gurib-Fakim, A. (2006). Medicinal plants: traditions of yesterday and drugs of tomorrow. *Molecular aspects of Medicine*, 27(1), 1-93.
15. Gurung, A.B., Ali, M.A., Bhattacharjee, A., AbulFarah, M., Al-Hemaid, F., Abou-Tarboush, F.M. (2016). Molecular docking of the anticancer bioactive compound proceraside with macromolecules involved in the cell cycle and DNA replication. *Genet Mol Res*, 15(2), 1-7.
16. Hamburger, M., Hostettmann, K. (1991). Bioactivity in Plants: The Link between Phytochemistry and Medicine. *Phytochemistry*, 30, 3864-3874.
17. Han, X., Shen, T., Lou, H. (2007). Dietary polyphenols and their biological significance. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.*, 950-988.
18. Harvey, A. (2000). Strategy for discovering drugs from previously unexploited natural products. *Drug Discovery Today*, 5, 294-300.
19. Ilavarasan, R., Mallika, M., Venkataraman, S. (2006). Anti-inflammatory and free radical scavenging activity of *Ricinus communis* root extract. *J Ethnopharmacol*, 103, 478-80.
20. Jena, J., Gupta, A.K. (2012). *Ricinus communis Linn*: a phytopharmacological review. *International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 4, 25–29.
21. Jugran, A. K., Bahukhandi, A., Dhyani, P., Bhatt, I. D., Rawal, R. S., and Nandi, S. K. (2016). Impact of altitudes and habitats on valerenic acid, total phenolics, flavonoids, tannins, and antioxidant activity of *Valeriana jatamansi*. *Applied Biochemistry and Biotechnology*, 179(6), 911–926.

22. Jugran, A. K., Bhatt, I. D., Rawal, R. S., Nandi, S. K., and Pande, V. (2013). Patterns of morphological and genetic diversity of *Valeriana jatamansi* Jones in different habitats and altitudinal range of West Himalaya, India. *Flora Morphology, Distribution, Functional Ecology of Plants*, 208, 13–21.
23. Jugran, A., Rawat, S., Dauthal, P., Mondal, S., Bhatt, I. D., and Rawal, R. S. (2013). Association of ISSR markers with some biochemical traits of *Valeriana jatamansi* Jones. *Industrial Crops and Products*, 44, 671–676.
24. Just, M.J., Recio, M.C., Giner, R.M., Cueller, M.U., Manez, S., Billia, A.R., Rios, J.L. (1998). Antiinflammatory activity of unusual lupine saponins from *Bupleurum fruticosens*, 64, 404-407.
25. Kang, S.S., Cordell, A., Soejarto, D.D., Fong, H.H.S. (1985). Alkaloids and flavonoids from *Ricinus communis*. *J. Nat. Prod.* 48 (1), 155–156.
26. Khairnar, A.K., Bhamare, S.R., Bhamare, H.P. (2012). *Calotropis procera*: An ethnopharmacological update. *Adv Res Pharm Biol*, 2,142-56.
27. Kim, M., Woo, Y. and Han, C. (2021). Current status of the spontaneous reporting and classification/coding system for herbal and traditional medicine in pharmacovigilance. *Integrative Medicine Research*, 10(1), 1-6.
28. Krings, U., Berger, R.G. (2001). Antioxidant activity of roasted foods. *Food Chem.*, 72, 223-229.
29. Lin, J.Y., Liu, S.Y. (1986). Studies on the antitumor lectins isolated from the seeds of *Ricinus communis* (castor bean). *Toxicon*, 24, 757–765. doi: 10.1016/0041-0101(86)90100-5.
30. Makonnen, E., Zerihun, L., Assefa, G., Rostom, A. (1999). Antifertility activity of *Ricinus communis* seed in female guinea pigs. *East African Medical Journal*, 76, 335–337.
31. Mann, J. (1978). Secondary Metabolism. *Oxford University press, London, pp.*, 154.
32. Marjorie, C. (1996). Plant products as antimicrobial agents. *Clinical Microbiol. Rev.*, 12, 564-582.
33. Mathur, A., Verma, S.K., Yousuf, S., Singh, S.K., Prasad, G., and Dua, V.K. (2011). Antimicrobial potential of roots of *R.communis* against pathogenic microorganisms. *International Journal of Pharma and Bio Sciences*, 2(1).
34. Meena, A.K., Yadav, A.K., Niranjana, U.S., Singh, B., Nagariya, A.K., Sharma, K., et al. (2010). A review on *Calotropis procera* Linn and its ethnobotany, phytochemical, pharmacological profile. *Drug Invent Today*, 2,185-90.
35. Mim, A.A., Chowdhury, S.A. (2015). Cytotoxic, anthelmintic and analgesic activities of the methanol extract of *Ricinus communis* (family: Euphorbiaceae). *Research & Reviews*, 5, 1–12.
36. Mueller-Harvey, I., McAllan, A.B. (1992). Tannins. Their biochemistry and nutritional properties. *In: Advances in plant cell biochemistry and biotechnology, Morrison IM, ed. JAI Press Ltd, London (UK)*, 1,151-217.
37. Nadkarni, A.K., Nadkarni, K.M. (1960). Indian material medica. *Popular book depot. Bombay, pp.* 69-71.

38. Nemudzivhadi, V., Masoko, P. (2014). In vitro assessment of cytotoxicity, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory activities of *Ricinus communis* (Euphorbiaceae) leaf extracts. *Evidence-Based Complementary and Alternative Medicine*, 625961. doi:10.1155/2014/62596.
39. Nobori, T., Miurak, K., Wu, D.J., Takabayashik, L.A., Carson, D.A. (1994). Deletion of cyclin-dependent kinase-4 inhibitor gene in multiple human cancers. *Nature*, 46, 753-756.
40. Nyarko, A.A., Addy, M.E. (1990). Effects of aqueous extract of *Adenia cissampeloides* on blood pressure and serum analyte of hypertensive patients. *Phytotherapy Res.*, 4(1), 25-28.
41. Okwu, D.E. (2001). Evaluation of chemical composition of medicinal plants belonging to Euphorbiaceae. *Pak Vet. J.*, 14, 160-162.
42. Okwu, D.E. (2004). Phytochemicals and vitamin content of indigenous species of southeastern Nigeria. *J.Sustain. Agric. Environ.*, 6(1), 30-37.
43. Okwu, D.E., Okwu, M.E. (2004). Chemical composition of *Spondias mombin linn.* plant parts. *J. Sustain. Agric. Environ.*, 6(2), 140-147.
44. Oloumi, H., and Hassibi, N. (2011). Study the correlation between some climate parameters and the content of phenolic compounds in roots of *Glycyrrhiza glabra*. *Journal of Medicinal Plant Research*, 5, 6011–6016.
45. Parihar, G., and Balekar, N. (2016). *Calotropis procera*: A phytochemical and pharmacological review. *Thai journal of pharmaceutical sciences*, 40(3).
46. Prasad, M.K., Rachaadiya, R.M., Shete, R.V. (2011). Pharmacological investigation on the wound healing effects of castor oil in rats. *International Journal of Universal Pharmacy and Life Sciences*, 1(1).
47. Quazi, S., Mathur, K., Arora, S. (2013). *Calotropis procera*: An overview of its phytochemistry and pharmacology. *Indian J Drugs*, 1, 63-90.
48. Ramos-Lopez, M.A., Perez-G, S., Rodriguez-Hernandez, C., Guevarafefer, P. and Zavala-Sanchez, M.A. (2010). Activity of *Ricinus communis* (Euphorbiaceae) against *Spodoptera frugiperda* (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae). *In African Journal of Biotechnology*, 9(9), 1359-1365.
49. Rampadarath, S., Puchooa, D. (2016). In vitro antimicrobial and larvicidal properties of wild *Ricinus communis L.* in Mauritius. *Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Biomedicine*, 6, 100–107. doi:10.1016/j.apjtb.2015.10.011.
50. Raquel, F.E. (2007). Bacterial lipid composition and antimicrobial efficacy of cationic steroid compounds. *Biochemica et Biophysica Acta*. 2500-2509.
51. Rawal, R. S., Pandey, B., and Dhar, U. (2003). Himalayan forest database—thinking beyond dominants. *Current Science*, 84, 990–994.
52. Rawat, S., Andola, A., Giri, L., Dhyani, P., Jugran, A., Bhatt, I. D., and Rawal, R. S. (2014). Assessment of nutritional and antioxidant potential of selected vitality strengthening medicinal plants. *International Journal of Food Properties*, 17, 703–712.

53. Rawat, S., Bhatt, I. D., and Rawal, R. S. (2011). Total phenolic compounds and antioxidant potential of *Hedychium spicatum* Buch. Ham. Ex D. Don in West Himalaya, India. *Journal of Food Component Analysis*, 24, 574–579.
54. Saber, H., Maharan, G.H., Rizkallah, M.M. (1969). Sterols and pentacyclic triterpenes of *Calotropis procera*. *Bull Fac Pharm*, 7, 91-104.
55. Saini, A.K., Goyal, R., Gauttam, V.K., Kalia, A.N. (2010). Evaluation of anti-inflammatory potential of *Ricinus communis* Linn leaves extracts and its flavonoids content in Wistar rats. *Journal of Chemical and Pharmaceutical Research*, 2(5), 690-695.
56. Salah, N., Miller, N.J., Pagange, G., Tijburg, L., Bolwell, G.P., Rice, E., Evans, C. (1995). Polyphenolic flavonoids as scavenger of aqueous phase radicals as chai breaking antioxidant. *Arc. Biochem. Broph.*, 2, 339-346.
57. Sandhyakumary, K., Bobby, R.G., Indira, M. (2003). Antifertility effects of *Ricinus communis* Linn. On rats. *Phytother. Res.* 17, 508–511.
58. Sani *et al.*, (2007). *Nig. Journ. Pharm. Sci.*, 6(2), 78 – 83.
59. Saxena, M., Saxena, J., Nema, R., Singh, D. and Gupta, A. (2013). Phytochemistry of Medicinal Plants. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry*, 11(6).
60. Sayed Ael-D., Mohamed, N.H., Ismail, M.A., Abdel-Mageed, W.M., Shoreit, A. (2016). Antioxidant and antiapoptotic activities of *Calotropis procera* latex on Catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) exposed to toxic 4-nonylphenol. *Ecotoxicol Environ Saf*, 128, 189-94.
61. Sharma, K., Kharb, R., Kaur, R. (2011). Pharmacognostical aspects of *Calotropis procera* (Ait.) R.Br. *Int J Pharm Bio Sci*, 2, 1-9.
62. Sharma, S., Singh, T. and Vijayvergia, R. (2009). Molluscicidal activity of some medicinal plants. *In Journal of Herbal Medicine and Toxicology*, 3(2), 155-157.
63. Shokeen, P., Anand, P., Murali, Y.K., Tandon, V. (2008). Antidiabetic activity of 50% ethanolic extract of *Ricinus communis* and its purified fractions. *Food and Chemical Toxicology*, 46, 3458–3466. doi:10.1016/j.fct.2008.08.020.
64. Shukla, O.P., Krishnamurthy, C.R. (1961). Properties and partial purification of bacteriolytic enzyme from the latex of *Calotropis procera* (Madar). *J Sci Ind Res*, 20, 109-12.
65. Sodipo, O.A., Akiniyi, J.A., Ogunbamosu, J.U. (2000). Studies on certain characteristics of extracts of bark of *Pansinystalia macruceras* (K schemp) picrre Exbeille. *Global J. Pure Appl. Sci.*, 6, 83-87.
66. Srivastava, P., Jyotshna, A., Gupta, N., Maurya, A.K., Shanker, K. (2014). New anti-inflammatory triterpene from the root of *Ricinus communis*. *Natural Product Research*, 28, 306–311. doi:10.1080/14786419.2013.861834.
67. Stray, F. (1998). The Natural Guide to Medicinal herbs And Plants. *Tiger Books International, London*, pp. 12-16.

68. Sunayana, N., Rawat, S., Rawal, R., Bhatt, I., Pathak, B., Fulekar, M.H. (2017). Soil constituents influence accumulation of phytochemicals and nutritional content in *Wrightia tinctora* of north Gujarat, india. *Indian Journal of Plant Physiology*.22.10.1007/s40502-017-0297-9.
69. Sundaresan, V., Shani, G., Verma, R. S., Padalia, R. C., Mahrotra, S., and Thul, S. T. (2012). Impact of geographic range on genetic and chemical diversity of Indian Valerian (*Valeriana jatamansi*) from north-western Himalaya. *Biochemical Genetics*, 50, 797–808.
70. Taur, D.J et al. (2011). *Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Biomedicine*, S13-S16.
71. Taur, D.J. (2011). *Lat. Am. J. Pharm*, 30 (6), 1226-8.
72. Taur, D.J., Patil, R. (2011). Antiasthmatic activity of *Ricinus communis* L. roots. *Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Biomedicine*, 1, S13–S16. Doi: 10.1016/S2221-1691(11)60113-5.
73. Tsala, D.E., Nga, N., Thiery, B.N., Bienvenue, M.T., Theophile, D. (2015). Evaluation of the antioxidant activity and the healing action of the ethanol extract of *Calotropis procera* bark against surgical wounds. *J Intercult Ethnopharmacol*, 4, 64-90.
74. Upasani, S.M., Kotkar, H.M., Mendki, P.S., Maheshwar, V.L. (2003). Partial characterization and insecticidal properties of *Ricinus communis* L. foliage flavonoids. *In Pest Management Science*, 59(12), 1349-1354.
75. Vaiyapuri, P.S., Ali, A.A., Mohammad, A.A., Kandhavelu, J., Kandhavelu, M. (2015). Time lapse microscopy observation of cellular structural changes and image analysis of drug treated cancer cells to characterize the cellular heterogeneity. *Environ Toxicol*, 30, 724-34.
76. Walton, N.J., Mayer, M.J., Narbad, A. (2003). Molecules of Interest: Vanillin. *Phytochemistry*, 63, 505- 515.